

GEN. MDSE.
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Pen-Tab

notebook

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New York 11385
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college ruled
8 1/2 in. x 11 in.

Müller

M Matte huts translated to mud brick like ^{to} stone
in Djoser complex

- Earliest Egyptian building culture - begins with
Hor Aha, Saggara N, area of capital:
Helwan, Giza, Abu Roash

p. 11 - No fore stages of development
M.b known since end of Nagada II, but no monumental
architecture

- Balce thought niched architecture developed from
Delta tradition of building in wood panels

- Delta places shown as (mudbrick) walled
bastioned enclosures on slate palettes

- Rounded corners to enclosure

- Bastions not regular

- But if walkway - parapet - then not
pisée but mudbrick - seen on
detailed Libyan Palette (?)

- Müller discusses sign on Narmer Palette;
one determined with niched wall enclosure, the
other with $\overline{\text{ss}}\overline{\text{v}}$ sign "Papyrus voyager"
• early word for Memphis Keimer
→ walled sign
for Sais → Papyrus

M How about "city dweller"
papyrus dweller (like Iraqi marsh dwellers)

p. 12.

Founding of Memphis

sudden and "The Wall"
"The White Wall" since Khasekhemwy

Experience must have been with Delta builders
used by Up. Eg. conquerors

Who had commerce with
Syrian coast

And so Delta folk had
experience - possibly -

in Mesop. building techniques

Saggara N Cemetery 1 Km long
"False Graves" of Kings under which
principally governors
princes and queens buried.

* Necking more complex than walls of Valley enclosures
in Abydos of Dyn. 1 and 2

System of Niches

↳ Broad niches in hind part,
decorative
smaller niches in fore part

p. 13

Painted with ^{colored} network design

False doors in recessed part taken
over from Door front of royal
mudbrick palace

Memphite Palace

p. 13

Founding of "Wall" of Memphis was a sudden and one-time act.

Possible only after taking Low. Eg. into service experienced in building and wood working from sea-relating - shipping activity

First brick palace under Hor-aha

Dyn. 1 Tombs at N. Saggara are image of palace

Image of Palace taken over - shown - in serekh, royal grave chambers of O.K., cult chambers of private tombs, decorative motif on sarcophagi

Shortly after Hor Aha - palace doorway in Hierakonpolis

Reps transfer of Northern building tradition to South. capital

p. 14

Elevation of Hierakonpolis Palace door - info from serekh development from Hor Aha until Djoser.

Serekh since Hor Aha with 2 or 3 doors increasingly clearer details - inspired by new m.b. palace

Djoser - Ivory plaques, ^{Unm. cl. Qaab} tombstones, 3 tower-like bastions flanking 2 palace doors

p. 14

Tower-like bastions also on stele of
Qa and Semerkhet

Later depictions - turrets or towers lacking,
space above door filled with windows,
with grating of balanced horizontal rungs
up to ceiling

So tower-like projections a means to
render forward spring of bastions?

Djet - serakh proportions (2:3) fairly exact
representation

p. 15

Windows over the doors

Over each small decorative niche of
projections is heraldic papyrus
stalks

p. 16

IV The Conversion of the Upper Egyptian
Tent Palace into the Memphite
Brick Palace

Serakh in early Horus names shows ^{schematically} only
entrance to tent palace; but since Har-Aha
the door front of mudbrick palace

3-Dimensional rep. in mudbrick of tent palace
not possible in rigid m.b. like in stone of later
Dioser complex

(?)

1st Dynasty forms are m.b. equivalent to
Zoser modelling in stone

p. 16

*

Conception of monumental M.B. palace comes out of fortified character of enclosure wall and bastions of surrounding Lower Eg. Residences or villages. The bastion-like projections of palace architecture of Eg. Archaic Period cannot be explained any other way.

Me. But these tombs not modeling a fortified town or residence in mudbrick, rather they purport to be a rigid model of wood and mat structure.

Other ideas must ^{come to} the execution in detail for validity: the projecting and recessed palace front is through the artistic system of variously broad and high niches broken up. The thick vertical arrangement gives the walls gravity, the ~~exchange~~ changing from small and door-like niches leaves the mudbrick wall permeable in appearance.

Me. Each of these tombs was like a brightly colored ^{wrap-around} false door. The false door of later tombs, was an abbreviation of a simulated royal girdle ^{pole and} ~~mat~~ ^{of royal design} ~~set~~ ^{in firm} ~~mat~~ solid mudbrick ^{at} ~~the~~ top of the escarpment overlooking the new town, haunted by the spirits of the King's agents and family members.

Matte decoration painting gives unmistakable interpretation of of palace's (tomb's) origin ^{descent} from the ~~created~~ girdle royal tent and its designation as the palace of the ruler of the Two Lands.

p. 16

Breaking up of exterior of strong m.b. walls thru
Nicked openings must rest on older building
methods which were also known in Mesopotamia

Nicked openings diminish indeed the wall strength,
in actuality they lend the wall greater
solidity. During building or after rain these
on the m.b. walls ^{they} allow moisture to evaporate more
quickly, while air and sunlight could better
penetrate.

Square recesses as in Djoser wall also openings
for such purposes. - possibly.

VI. Papyrus Stalk Pair on the Memphite Palace.

- First time on Djed Stela
- Always on decorative niches, near one small
entrance doors in recesses.

Müller compares to papyrus stem and wall
enclosure next to fallen pair on Narmer
Palette. Keimer, Schott, Sethe: wider
designation for Memphite name?

2 stems and blossoms stylized in bound
pair to give ^{old} name of Lower Egypt.

The two label signs amalgamated in
Papyrus-pair emblem inset in actual wall.

Papyrus dweller, Town dweller?

Or Papyrus stalk construction.

Does mat/wood construction relate more to L. Eg.

because more bldg. material - tall stalks, wood
nearby?

VII. Royal Grave Superstructures of Early Dyn. 1

p. 17

p. 18

N. Cemetery is "False grave" (Cenotaph) cemetery where King present after his death

Here British tradition followed - ruler in his house present for eternity.

As King of Two Lands, the monumental building expressed both British Maat - hut and Up. Eg. Tent palace transported to Memphis as m.b. palace.

Outer appearance must reflect dualistic character

2 elements and traditions not mixed, two elements as self standing bodies, as an inner core construction and as niched outer wall

Inner core reflects ^{towering} British palace with vaulted roof, niched outer wall is Memphite palace

*

Ground outline shows two elements combined one in another like Double Crown Up & Low Eg.

p. 18

Palace front of tomb superstructures not formal or measured copy of palace. As excavated only 2m high. Wall thickness enormous: ca. 2.80 m. Breadth of false door in recesses ^{height} and ~~width~~, indicated in 2 cases by round ^{wood} balls only 1.55 - far too low.

A complete picture of these tomb superstructures is given by outside of 4th-5th Dyn. sarcophagi which render palace facade. Here the palace door takes only about half height. Here palace door only, half height of entire front and wall surfaces over the doors are set with lattice (or grating) window openings. On Djehuti stela door ^{claims to be} about $\frac{2}{3}$ height of the building, height. First Dyn tombs show a palace arrangement following at changed proportions, ^{because of} with multiple repeating of door motif and with rich window-like external decoration which distanced it from its prototype, yet brought to expression an ideal.

p. 17

To what extent, however, ~~was~~ the window-like forms, with which the relief representations of O.R. tombs and sarcophagi decorated the palace facade, ^{were} represented on the m.b. arch. of the tomb superstructures through projecting collars and set-backs, is on the basis of what's preserved ~~not~~ no longer to be determined. Supported height ^{if niched outer side} must depend on relief repr. of palace facade, which correspond with one another in their proportions and details.

M. P. 15 }
1957, 153f }

Lauer's determination

Top of false door in one of recesses: $1.55 \text{ m} = 3 \text{ cubits}$
= about $\frac{1}{2}$ height of decorative niches of projections

From here to round wood underneath the papyrus emblem 3.10 m (6 cubits)

^{Gives} $\approx \frac{3}{4}$ total building height
Facade height 4 m (= 8 cubits) from base of building to concluding frieze

So whole building ca. 5 m (10 cubits)

Müller

But how was the upper end - the roof formed?

The Sarcophagi of Dyn 4 & 5 "as three dimensional reproductions of Dyn I tomb superstructures as a rule with an even ^{arched} vaulted ceiling between the high ~~the~~ head sides. For considerations of maneuverability the Sarcophagus lid is of granite or limestone thick, indicates nonetheless the form of the Buta hut as a firmly fixed component of the tomb superstructure

Sarcophagus of Mentkaure and few others of Dyn 4 have instead of vaulted, a flat lid with a high throat (cornice) under a horizontal round bar. The high cornice as a crowning corresponds to the hieroglyph pr nw (Low Eg. palace) with half-rounded arched roof to form a mat-hut with upper high cornice and round poles on the corners. Sarcophagi indicate pr

nw because of some form Evidence: - Sarcophagi of 12 Dyn. since Sesostris II

- Taking up of niched enclosure walls
- Sesostris III referral to Djoser layout"

- Sarcophagi niched arrangement
- Sarcophagi - niched facade take up half height the sarcophagus
- Towing above is Buta Grave form

p 20

Coop. Amenemhat statue and m.k. drawings at Hierakonpolis

The Buto grave ~~found above~~ dominated also this enclosure wall already as doubled, its recessed and horizontal sides were fixed with a mat decoration. In the 12th Dyn. the tradition yet lived that this part of the sarcophagus represented the Buto tomb.

Certainly ~~in the 12th Dyn.~~ this mat decoration, which in the 12 Dyn. also appeared on Kanopic chests (with vaulted ceilings!), ~~was~~ was not needed as a ~~and~~ ornament on the sarcophagi. ~~The evidence of~~

The outer vaulted sarcophagus roof on the grave of Sesostris-ankh in Licht which on the inner side is set with an especially carefully executed mat decoration testifies to this.

In Lauer's reconstruction this imp. element, the Buto grave, building ~~is~~ which towered above the niched "mud brick palace" is entirely disregarded, though sarcophagi of the Old and much more of the Middle Kingdoms have truly preserved this element [Müller adds this element as a counter suggestion in Abb. 13]

The architecture of Up. Eg. tendency, especially the 4th Dyn. Pyramids and ~~smooth~~ flat mastabas had for the realization of Low. Eg. concepts no other room for display or development to arise as in interior of the grave on the walls of the ~~to~~ cult chamber and on sarcophagi.

XII.

ROYAL TOMB SUPERSTRUCTURES

SAQQARA NORTH

p. 28

Niche Depth	Name	Tomb No	Length x W.dth	Greatest Preserved Height	Wall Thick. Outer
Large Small					
1.20 .25	<u>HOR ANA</u>	3357	41.60 x 15.55	1.75	2.4 - 2.65
1.10 .25	<u>DJER</u>	3471	41.30 x 16.00	1.00	^W 2, 2.65 - 2.75
1.10 .25	<u>MERNEITH</u>	3503	42.60 x 16.00	2.20	2.70 - 2.75
1.10 .25	<u>DJET</u>	3504	49.50 x 20.00	2.35	2.90

Earliest, show in ground plan a thick enclosure wall arranged with the complicated palace decoration enclosing a rectangle which ^{was} through essentially weaker rectilinear tapered walls divided ^{into} checker board-like. Within the three long rows of chambers there was indicated "the middle strip five adjacent aligned chambers that go together; one large middle, the burial chamber and on either side two smaller for the burial offerings. In the tombs of Hor Ana and Merneith there five chambers are in similar moderately deeper laid out; in the tombs of Djer and Djed the middle burial chamber - as in Giza V - is sunk deeper ^{in the descent} than the storage chambers. The Up. Eg. pit grave made its influence increase, also ^{counted} in the tomb superstructure of the Lower Eg. residence. This group of five chambers corresponds to the core building of the tomb at Nagada. In tomb layout of Saqqara North is however, the demarcation against the rest of the chambers and the emphasized ^{given} as single standing element enclosed by thick walls. However also with these superstructures

The Buto tomb with vaulted ceiling must have considerably towered above being set against the outer wall of niched arrangement like tomb of Shepseskaf, Khentkawes, reconstructed superstructure of Napada tomb

Outer wall at Saggara N thickness from 2.5 to 2.9 m, niches 1.20 m. in mudbrick work; rest of walls @ 1.00 - 1.50 m thick have been sufficient to ~~take the~~ carry the corresponding flat walls (back side) of the Butish tomb, particularly the system of the dividing walls of the chambers of the outer wall additionally supported and the entire construction ~~in the~~ was strongly braced.

If one accepts with Erms that the outer chamber that surrounded the burial and grave good chambers were filled to top with sand, the burial chamber with a ~~base~~ ceiling, ^{balk} decks and a first sand piling upon it and underneath the roof afterwards ^{covered} with a ~~base~~ balk-ceiling and sand pile ~~over~~, then the possibility ^{is filled} of a ~~solid~~ firm stability of a high towering building. With a simple m.b. layer over the uppermost sand bed the ~~flat~~ smooth vaulting between the high end walls have ~~been~~ found their upper completion

Stadelmann Pyramiden

p. 15.

HOR AHA

3357

Double enclosure wall

41.60 x 15.55 m (80 x 30 cubits)

9 Niches on long sides

3 Niches on short sides

possibly 5.25 m high (10 cubits)

North side } Boat Grave - First example
Cult layout } Graveries

p. 16

No special cult place in mastaba -

Each deep niche fitted with false door

Dead came and go

Not at Hacha → Models bulls heads w/ actual horns in front of and in niches

Burial chamber and storage rooms - N and S of grave pit - in a trench 1.35 m deep in surface, 19.10 x 2.90

Divided by cross walls in 5 chambers

Middle one larger = burial chamber

Walls decorated with multi-colored mats on mud plaster

p. 17

Ceiling - Wood beams and planks

Sand and gravel piled above

Tumulus ≈ 1 m high - reminiscent of those in Umm el Qaab

Rich finds of ceramics, stone vessels, and offerings also clay models of rhinoceros horns at

Stadelmann

comes in fill of superstructure - magical
protection of grave

N. Cem. General

Hor Aha = Menes

Fonded Memphis

INBA HEDJ

"White walls"

Ptah Temple (?)

Direct Line to Cemetery

And

Royal City already?

Must take care

Sparse texts leave open possibility that during
the Thinis period (Dyn. 1-2) no
one permanent royal residence

King and court travel from place to place

King and Temple

South: Hierakonpolis State god Horus

Sailed north Ombos "Gold City" Seth

Niche Tomb Prince or Neit hotep
Sealings, ivory labels of Hor Aha

53 x 26 m

100 x 50 cubits

(over)

Stadelmann p. 20

Until middle of Dyn 1 the tombs ~~also~~
measures and form of grave room and checker-
board ^{filled} superstructure very similar

Udimu - long reign, real significant change

3 tombs ascribed to him in Saggara

Adjacent S 3036, S 3035

Queen?

largest Achaic grave

First time Entrance from east corridor

Grave could remain open after completion for later
access for funeral

Beautifully ^{heavy} hemistone ^{particulis} - the first of this type
in long line, made possible closing of
corridor after the funeral

Solved problem of security of mastaba grave
and accompanying goods, allows in-filling
but leaves access

p. 21

Burt Emery, G.T.

- Refs. Fa. Key Mon. GT III, p. 4 (no. I)
- 3357 HOR AHA 60, 63, 35
 - 3471 ZER DJER "Name found on some of the jar scalings." GT II, 13
 - 3504 Junker DJET 9 (1940), 139.
 - 3035 DEN
 - 3038 Stadelman ANDU B MOAIR 28 (1971) 128 f.
 - 3505 QAI
 - 3503 MER-NEIT
 - 3507 HER-NEIT

3471 - DJER GT I

Main Walls N. 15.15 m

p. 14

3505 GT III, 6, E 41.20

3506 GT III, 41 W 41.30

3507 2.00 - 2.75 m thick

p. 15

Niches Large 2.10 max width
 1.10 " depth
 Small .50 m width
 .25 " depth

Plantation 3036 GT I, 73
 small
 (see previous list) in wall trench 1.50 m
 the wall 1.60 m

Pottery in-situ in front of niches
3503 GT11, 139

Ox head in niche Period C 3038
GT1, pl. 27B

Pavement Holes

Mer Neith 3503 GT11, 131, Fig 201

Hör Aha p. 4, Fig. 6

Buto Cemetery

Reps. Fa Khry Monuments of Senefertu I
60, fig. 35

Junker MDAIK 9 (1940), 1-39

Stadelmann MDAIK 27 (1971) 122 f.

See LÄ I, 887 "Buto's Begräbnis"

Bulls Heads

3505 GT III, 6, 8

3506 GT III, 41

3507 GT III, 75

Pavement Holes

3505 Corridor GT III, 7
Stadelmann takes as tree pits
Pyramiden p. 25

{ decayed wood
1.75 m springs
20 cm deep
16 cm diam.

Plantation 3036 GT I, 73
small tree remains (rosts) in ~~small~~ trench 0.70 m deep
1.5 m wide
tree every 1.60 m.

Tumulus

3506 GT III, 41
 3507 GT III, 73, 77
 3038
 3471 ^{see mention} GT III, 73

Grandaes

Den ? Neska Tomb X GT I, 107
 Den Setka 3506 GT III, 43
 Pa Merka 3505 GT III
 Den Hemaka }
 Den Ankhka } ³⁰³⁵
 Medjedka } → 3036 jar sealings
 Ka nj } together in 3506 GT III, 61
 Her-nata
 Djer-Den Sekhka 3507
 Andjib Den Nebetka 3038 GT I, 82 Name on
 Den Andjib Sabu 3111 GT I, 95 Grandaes

Sm priests
 iry-pets
 of mr
 h3ty-c
 nd-hr Councillor
 of h3p hr ib "Ruling in Kinsir Heart"
 Treasurer - Nes-ka Tomb X
 3505
 3500
 3338
 3120
 3121
 X
 3041
 3509

GT I, 71
 Hemaka }
 Ankhka } ed mr Hr stnt m
 Medjedka } best
 GT III, 70, No. 33 smt necropolis
 hrt desert

Governor of District of "Promoting
 the Necropolis of Horus"

MUD SEALINGS

OFFICIALS

- 335 Sekhka
- Neska
- 3421 Setka
- Hemaka
- 2185 Ankhka
- Medjedka
- 3504 NiKa
- Nebetka
- 3035 Sabu
- Merka
- 3036 Horneith
- Hor-Aha
- 350 Mesenka

MUD SEALINGS

	<u>Ruler(s)</u>	<u>Official(s)</u>
350 3357	Hor AHA	-
3471		
350 2185		
3504		
GT III, 32f 3035	5 seals of - QA	Merka stela 2 Merka impressions
3036		
311 3506		
3507		
3505 3038		
3111		
3505 3505		
3500		
3338		
3120		
3120 3121		
X		
3121 3041		
3503	Merneith	

MUD SEALINGS

REF

Ruler

Official

3357

Architecture

3471

Stretched mats on board faces of painting
pilasters

2185

Narrow raised surfaces on upright wood
parts

3504

Chairs of staves = wood lockers

GT III, 32f

3035

QA (5 serckhs)

• Netermerib 2 Merka impressions

• MERKA STELA

• SEKHEMKA

3036

direct and deliberate correspondance between
mixing and elements of wood frame

3506

reed mat

3503

leave center

sculptural treatment of elements in broken structure

3507

Showing the construction of the wood frame

3038

accentuating the primary skeleton

Carthage

letting all elements express the main

Sel

3111

fractive skeleton

Intertone

Arch

3505

Elaborate mixing of a sculptural
treatment of skeleton system

3500

3338

3120

3121

3041

Wood Frame, Reed Mat
Architecture

x

Stretched mats on broad faces of projecting
pilasters
Narrow vertical surfaces are upright wood
posts

Chairs of ellipses = wood lashings

Very direct and deliberate correspondence between
niching and elements of wood frame,
reed mat

Massive system
Sculptural treatment of elements - fictive skeleton

"Showing the construction" eg. Mies van der Rohe
Articulated skeletons
accentuating the primary skeleton

C. Norberg-Schulz
Intentions in
Architecture

letting all elements express their role
fictive skeleton
Elaborate niching is a sculptural
treatment of skeleton system

First time
Nagada tomb is potation
More house-like within enclosure
to 5-room house
No substructure - Delta tradition?
Hot mid
No more care building
Instead a grave pit

North Sappara Development

①

Hor AHA

Rectangular pit cut in gravel and rock
19.10^{N2S} x 2.90^{E-W} 1.35 in deep

Checkerboard patterned cross walls
divide into 5 rooms

Central - burial chamber

Side rooms magazines

Roofed by l. wood beams 10 cm diam.

Spaced 25 cm

2. Planks

3. Reed mats

4. M.b.

27 Magazines by unbanded cross walls
Filled with sand - false floor, 1m high

Magazines prob. like in Hemaka roofed by
log beams + wood planks + reed mats
+ brick roofing

FIRST TOMB

Megada tomb is prototype
More house-like within enclosure

↳ 5-room house

No substructure - Delta tradition?

Hor Aha - ^{mid} room goes deeper
No more core building
Instead a grave pit

72-73 310000 N. Saggara Development (2)

Mastaba 2185 Djoser great stone beams
over grave chamber

Major innovations in reign of Dcn

3036 } stepped
Pyramid 3035 Henaka } Entrance from
E Corridor

Grave could be entered
after completion sealed
by mastaba superstructure

FIRST PORTCULLIS SLAB closures

- Lon. line to Pyramid corridors
allow closure after funeral

Allowed closure of burial chamber
& side mags.

So tumulus 3471 GT I 131F

GT III 73

3507 GT III, 73

Seed of Pyramid

ADJIB 3038

72-73 SAQQARA PYRAMIDS An Overview

- Plateau chosen because above Nile Valley
Choke point
- Largest necropolis from Dyn 1 - Coptic Christian
- Central Plateau is 2.5×2.5
- Take in S. Saggara and ~~Abu Sir~~ Abu Sir
7.5 m long
- Center piece of site ~~tableau~~ is Step Pyramid
- ~~At~~ Perhaps already Zone of royal ~~to~~ enclosures as early as Dyn. 2
 - Galleries of Ni netjer, Hetepsekhemwi
 - Mysterious Giza el Mudir
- Why so far out in desert?
 - Step Pyr. no causeway to connect to valley
 - Wadi was connection - straight to Giza, Sekhemkhet, Zoser
- Hiatus, remaining Dyn. 3, ~~all~~ all of Dyn. 4
 - Sneferu Maidum
 - Dahshur
 - Giza Kings
- Userkaf return but now pyramids need access to valley - dif configuration - NAT. LAKES
- Abu Sir
 - Rough ~~the~~ NE-SW diagonal as at Giza, Um el Qaab, ^{Central Saggara}
 - Stars in Orion's belt
- S. Saggara Djedkare Isesi

Shesepkaf
Return

Djoser	Sahure
Serkhen Khet	Neuserre
Usertaf	Nefertkare
Unas	Raneferet
Teti	
Merenre	
Pepi I	
Pepi II	
Merykare	
Abi	
Djedkare Isesi	

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Unas - Life 2 ~~1~~ guard posts,
1st and 1st K of Dyn. 5
flank Zoser complex

position must have been of some
importance - witness need of long
causeway

Teti adds to diagonal

Pepi I and his two sons return to S.

Saggara

About on line of principal run field

Mn-afk "The Perfection of Pepi Endures"

Pyramid Town

Simulation - of (now) masonry

and red mud/brick

Meaning of place at another time

Unadorned masonry - walls

Meaning of place at another time

Here act of collaboration - from the dead

See Murray, 1985

Statues governing every form
going forth
comp. Sta Dyr. tomb of Ty

Circuitousness

Circulation - / m entrance - check granite plug
and Funerol

Cartese

Model of Funerol

complex, model of tomb

Petrify to Perpetuate

Unique, not repeatable act Stadelmann p.67

Netjer Khut complex is like an architectonic
sign-list of sacred building hieroglyphs.

See Karp "Vocabulary of forms"

Connect with codify

Yet many forms never used again

Firsts - first colonnade, hypostyle, portico
life-size statues, torus moulded cornice

74-77 STEP PYRAMID

General

- 3rd Dyn. beginnings
- Question of Beit Khallaf
- Sudden new order of magnitude
 - Size Not an narrow entrance
 - Material
 - Craftsmanship
- Name - check Stadelmann
- Djosor / Imhotep ^{codification} rep. as founder of Stone Building.
- Name Liberation of Gods gbkw ntrw
BIFAO 81 (1981), 163
- No tombs within enclosure except few burials of latest period in Saggara - a place w/ burials of every age

Note panels carved in enclosure wall after blocks set

Note: all doors left open

Simulation - of (now) mudbrick and reed mat / wood

Enclosure wall squares - built end of wood reinf.
Log ceilings - eg. Temple T
So now simulation of simulation of original reed bldgs.

Heb sed see Layer I, p. 6, n. 2

Meaning of stages of construction

- Unaddressed questions works, economy, quarry
- ^{Certain} Many forms never again executed or not again for long time
 - Layer I, 144 engaged columns
 - caryatids
 - faience capitals
 - fluted columns
 - faience tile door
- Keep act of codification
See Anatomy, p. 95

Although created vocabulary of forms

Building Askew

Kaiser MPAIK 1969

Paneling on Colonnade S wall - 16m long

Small buildings in Falkecirke at Abydos

Peribsen 12 x 9 m

Khasekhemwy 18 x 15 m

} with niche decor

Near SW entrance

Netjer-khet Building Askew:

Not Kaiser reconstr. 30 m x 15 m (p. 9, Abb. 2)

Shaft (Lower degrés, I, 115) 25+ m.
deep.

Corridor with 6 galleries under sanctuary

Oblong chambers connected at E end

S.m.
Open doors ←

niche winding passage to small

S.m. open
door ←

chamber

Kaiser

Living palace of King or successor

Helek

Statue palace

Kemp

"Taken palace"

Layer. I, 178-179

S. Court.

3/4° off ^{orientation} ~~axis~~ of enclosure wall
to west

Parallelogram

3 Faces rich decorated

Closed door with simulated hinge

Originally double leaf door, 3m wide

Not paved, virgin soil too low, banked up w/
waste of limestone over which a layer
of soil. cm of ^{reddish} clay mixed w/ desert pebbles
Resembles natural soil of region

Altar

limestone 60 cm from casing of P2

36.50 from its SE angle

Ramp to platform, 1 m high, 7 x 7.4 m

Before ramp a ^{cow} skull with large horns

buried in hole

B-stones

Pyramid P_i

4th PROJECT

Stadelmann
P_i and P_{i'}
still using small
blocks, on no side
is smaller material
higher than M₃
p.54

Still core and casing, but profound difference

Abandoned horizontal beds

Adapted accretions, each inclined 15° to 17°
so far beds

{ Bigger and better blocks
Blocks no longer packed in abundant clay
mortar - laid simply with aid of mortar

Casing blocks no longer bevelled like preceding M₁-M₃

Added 5 1/2 cubits to E face M₃ (2.88m)
and all sides of mastaba

Length 163 cubits E-W

Width 147 cubits N-S

Casing quickly abandoned

Comp M₃

Core completed

If ^{steps} same width as P₂, P_i only 4 steps

p.18

Massif added to N - for cut chambers

Comparable to that N of STomb

Trial for Funerary temple - T₁

Small blocks in horizontal beds

P_{i'}

5th PROJECT

- Increase of P_i to N and and West

105 200 cubits

Conserved casing of P_{i'} on S. and E

118 225 cubits

Covered T₁

~~Casing~~ Facing of P_{i'} equal to P_i + M₃

= 8 cubits

Pro^{west}longed P_i by 62 cubits "theoretically"

West face at Tumulus for height 4.70m

Laver says tumulus leans against Pyramid

Massif of P1, would have had 6 steps
When P1, abandoned for P2, not above 4th step

Each step formed of 2 accretion layers
average 10-11 cubits wide = 5.24m -
5.76m
Facing = 3rd accretion 5 cubits = 2.62

First ^{inside} ~~of each~~ accretion of each step serves
as backing of facing of step above

So each step is moved in $\approx$ 12 cubits from
previous = 6.29m

Steps terminate at a bevel of 20°-23°
and not at sharp corner

STADELMANN on P1

P1 little more than a ramp ^{dressed m-3} with better materials
and methods - or so builders must have thought
to contain base of local limestone for P2

P1 hardly built up over M2

2 layer building method - core first, then casing
= P1 actually built - not so

P1' an extension of P1 to N and W
or pedestal, ^{or base} foundation for P2

Over built w/ larger masonry format

So no P1 to 4 steps

P²

Lower, degree, I, p. 23-25

For Lower, P² simple modification of P¹'
by light accretion to N side, 5 cubits wide
from base to summit of 4th step. From
here to top building is unity - no structural
discontinuity. So that top of Pyramid is wider
than 5 cubits

P² - Still bigger blocks

Blocks range from .48 to .52

Masonry more careful

Casing ^{or} Facing 3 cubits thick

E & S base of 1st step

Added to facing of P¹'

E & S.

{ So total casing is 8½ cubits
of fine limestone

W.

{ From 4.70 from base
Facing is 5 cubits

N

P² facing 5 cubits + Facing P¹' 8 c.
= 13 cubits

But with addition of accretion
on N that covers P¹' facing
have 5 cubits facing P² and
when accretion does not cover P¹'
facing, obtain 6 cubits total
facing

N-S dimension 200 cubits P¹' + 3 c + 5 c = 208

E-W " 225 P¹' + 2 x 3 cubits = 231

Vertical 114.23 re. Sea Level - Survey of Egypt
pt. 3-40

p. 24

58.63 above average level of base
Originally 1.30 above ~~the~~ current top

P2

Lower, degrees, I p. 24

Discrepancy of .76 m from E face - best
conserved, between middle of face where
begins casing, and NE Angle when
0.12

$$\begin{array}{r} \text{Ma} \quad \text{so} \quad .64 \quad \text{OR} \quad -0.12 \\ \quad \quad \quad \frac{-.12}{.52} ? \quad \quad \quad \frac{.64}{.76} ? \end{array}$$

- Builders probably measured in whole numbers from upper edge to upper edge of steps of pyramid
- Side angles of steps vary from $71^\circ - 76^\circ$ most near 74°

S. Tomb Stadelmann, Lower, degrés, I, 94-98

Superstructure

Chapel

N. Tomb Chapel

SW Angle of S. Court

Massif of juts out to N from wall

43 m x 17.35

N and E face fine limestone, panelled - continuation of S. Court wall

Cobra head frieze - cobra above each panel

Sanctuary - vestibule E-W to N-S chamber

Σ Statue Chamber?

Fine masonry badly damaged - so hard to reconst.

Simulated open door?

Superstructure

Set into enclosure wall

{ note t3yt - shroud
t3yt, shrouded one
vizier, Osiris
or Buta goddess

Long superstructure 160 x 25 cubits

Massif cased in fine limestone

Rise above wall terrace by 4 m

~~Vertical~~ End walls near vertical (slight batter 3-4 cm/meter)

Long side walls inclined by 6°

Casing 2 1/2 to 3 cubits

Casing is inclined courses like pyramid P1-2

S. Tomb - Stadelmann, Pyramiden

p 49 Chapel with statue chamber - ^{abbreviated} reduced version of N. Temple

M Orientation E-W, ^{exit} entrance leads out to W at SW Corner, recalls SW orientation of openings in rows of subsidiary graves, at Umm el-Qaab and archaic "false door" in Diet's tomb

1. ...
2. Wall of yellow limestone ...
3. ... filled with earth, sand, stone ...

1. ...
2. ...
3. ...

Heb Sed Complex

Lower I, p. 730-

Only access from colonnade

50 m. passage

1. Rectangular court, 2 series of chapels, W & E.
2. Second court passed rounded wall w/ Temple T
3. Labyrinthine passages in massif to S

5. Platform - 2 stairways, 1 m high

= hieroglyph for Sed Festival 2 stairways in date

p. 131

Model of Sed complex

Like S Tomb + Chapel
 here hieroglyphic
 architectural hieroglyphs

Hieroglyphs for Sed

correspond to pavilions and stairway platform

A. W. massif

Composition: 1. Fine limestone facing $\approx$ 1.55 thick

2. Wall of yellow limestone of desert

apart w/ facing leans

3. Core filled with earth, sand, chips w/ desert limestone retaining walls here and there

W. Row:

1. ^{edifice} Torus molded facade - sh ntr form

Bound to one to N back back wall,

only its distinct roof emerges

Simulated closed door in center of face

Statue Chamber (?) on S of front

enclosure

2. 2 Chapelles with ³ fluted columns

Stairways ascend to large niche on S. side of facade

Shrines
 on
 pedestals
 Lower's
 subbasement

p. 132.

3 2 Statues of Netjerykhet, N and S

M These stairways up to ~~to~~ within per wr type chapel is more glyph for Sed than platform

After Sh ntr 5 following chapels have same form: stone images of wood frame construction ^{between two tall pilasters on either side} with hung mats, lightly vaulted roof covered by 3 thin fluted pillars - Form of per wer. In front, low walls, c. 2.10 m, defined two parallel chambers forming indirect ^{unroofed} passage back to a small nich ~~set~~ ^{built} into fine limestone facing at ~~lower~~ ^{lower} ~~left~~ (south) of chapel center of chapel - statue niche. Entrance to passage ~~also~~ ^{also} at far south ~~but one is fixed to~~ ^{through simulated open door} on line with niche, but one is fixed by partition wall between chambers to turn right, then left at end of first room, left again to go back to niche. This indirect ²¹⁹⁻²²⁹ passage was characteristic of ~~many~~ ^{many} other structures in the Netjerykhet complex, ~~in fact~~ ^{at the SE corner} the entrance end of ~~domestic~~ ^{domestic} ~~houses~~ ^{houses} and palaces in general. Picket fence w/ 6 stakes and cross pieces.

Following 2 similar, no statue niches
Niche in lower S corner

Chapel X niche placed laterally in NE corner
Middle of Base of 2nd Chamber an small chamber
W. Side Sh ntr form

3 More chapels of per wer form

Lower, 4,

E Chapels numbered 6, 7, 8, like 3, 4, 5

Next court penetrates deep into massif

Then 2 More Per Wer 9, 10,

No. 10 no zig zag passage in front only
open court

To enter 10, have to use winding ^{divided} court passage
at N end of Heb Sed court. Next to 10 is
J, again a sh ntr form - exact size of
sh ntr form at north end of court

Last edifice, J, sh ntr form again

Row flanked on N & S by sh ntr ends
one in middle

Door in N gives access to small statue chamber

Socle w/ 4 pairs of feet

Netjer, Khet

Hetep-her-nebti

Int-Ka-s

Queen

p. 134 No ^{exit} entrance from Heb Sed Court on N.

p. 142 **B.** EAST MASSIF

Backed by massif shared with E side enclosure
wall

E Chapels more badly destroyed, plan visible
Series of 12 chapels, fronted by winding open-air
passage created by dividing court, simulated open
doors, niche in front of chapel parallel to facade

Lave, degrés, I, 142

E Chapels reduced in width

$\left. \begin{array}{l} 12 \text{ Chapels on E,} \\ 10 \text{ paves on W} \end{array} \right\} 22 = \text{Nomes?}$

No torus molding on basement or on small walls
No columnettes

Facade outlined by torus molding on arch,
by verticals in relief on 2 sides, 6cm wide
Serrated few mm.

Facade outline analogous to the W Chapels
12 Chapels on E similar Facade

At S. end of row 2 divided court corridor
much elongated before badly destroyed
massif, unclear ground plan

C. Statues of Netjer, Khat from here?

- Appear to have been caryatids engaged in a facade. Totally new in Eg. Architecture
- 3 Statues found, but many large blocks to make more (?) abandoned
Osirid, holding flail and scepter
- 2.20 m high
- Abacus to support ^{cornice} coping stone
- Situated ^{intended} in massif R and/or further S. at entrance into Heb Sed court
- Or in niches, like high-~~rel.~~ rel. of statues found in O.K niches

Lower, degrees, I, 145

D. DAIS

5.30 x 4.50

2 Stairs - 3 Steps, bottom rounded

Trace of light walls at SW angle

Torus edge 15cm diam

Double pavilion of Heb Sed

E. Temple T

Original height 6.90 p. 150

Separate court w. of Sed Chapels

Earliest torus molding (rolled binding)

ORIGIN OF EGYPTIAN CORNICHE

Kemp } { One of few "real" buildings of Step Pyramid
Complete interior of rooms & corridors
rolled binding
tops of corbel reduced to plain frieze

- 2 doors - to S and E, simulated open ^{16 flutes}
- Kind of hypostyle - 3 fluted columns engaged to tongue walls
- Access to 3 courts along W of structure
- To N to "sanctuary" Djed frieze
- Back room (bedroom?)

p. 148-9 Column

Band above base @ .70 m @ 2.5-3 cm wide

So in Mansion of N & S, Temple

Composed of courses of masonry, each course of various 4-5 blocks

Original total height 5m. 95

F.

SE Corner Massif

Lower, degrees, I
p. 153

Maze of turning corridors, chambers, small sanctuaries

Orientation of sanctuaries appear to play no role

One had access to these corridors before arriving at Heb Sed court, through simulated open door

Chamber 2 - 2 simulated closed doors in S. wall

Small chamber with simulated open door

Corridors probably covered, or could have been, nearly every where

1. Abnormal placement of pits - not in principal
2. Simulated to P₁ = offering pits
3. Pits found at Heb Sed
4. Pits probably not where it S. chamber
5. Heb Sed court
6. Pits probably found in gate

Symbolic indices of N & S constructed by emblematic plants

2 Notional sanctuaries: Pan Wen - N-Khu, Pan Nui - But

Residence
Treasury

Mansions of N and S

Lower degrees, I, 154f

Access to M. South - Through colonnade

Tombs or chapels of princesses - so Fifth because:

Simulated open door

1. Many fragments of stela found in proximity of names Hetep-herkhebi and Inkhos.
2. Situation near corner (NE) of monument resembles position of queens pyramids
3. Each have a serdab-like chamber in addition to niche at end of winding corridors. Serdab resembles that behind serdab of Djoser statue

Access to Mansion of North

Lower contra hypothesis

Turn at NE corner of Pyramid, enter serdab

1. More stela of princesses found in S. Court + North other places in complex
2. Abnormal placement of pits - not in principal massif.
3. Similarity to P₃ = Offering pits like those found at Bat Khallaf
4. Papyrus column - emblematic of N and probability of street of S. does not suggest princesses' tombs
5. Like Heb Sed chapels resemble houses, no funerary character of Achaic mastabas
6. Princesses probably buried in galleries under E of Pyramid

Symbolic edifices of N + S. characterized by emblematic plants

2 National sanctuaries: Per Wer Nekhen
Per Nu Buto

Residences

Treasuries

Access to M. South. - Through colonnade,
S Great Court to SE corner of Pyramid.
Simulated open door

↳ Inside to R, a 3-niche sanctuary
↳ Long court along entire E face of Pyramid

Middle of E wall, simulated open door
to Court of ~~South~~ Mansion of South

Access to Mansion of North:

Turn at NE corner of Pyramid, enter serdab
court, turn right sharply, corridor to Mansion of
North

p. 157

FACADES OF BOTH MANSIONS

Each

- 4 engaged columns 50 cm diam base
- Framed by uprights
↳ differ
- 2 Facades about same length
- Each w/ off-axis entrance
- Corridor to small cruciform sanctuary w/ 3 niches
M. N. has 2 add. niches at ends of approach corridor
- Corridors roofed by log imitates
- Toward extreme SW corner, blocked corridor
to small chamber - probable serdab for
royal statue

Mansions of N and S.

Lower, degree I,

Columns

Kha Khao Faeng

p. 159f

Columns attached, 13 concave flutes

2-3 cm Band @ 60 cm above base

↳ Not a tie with flutes - this not a bundle of stems, flutes hollowed

≈ .50 cm diam. base

.28 " " at capital

2 Center columns about 12 m high

45 higher than 2 flanking

Capitals like pillars in Hab Sed court but twice the size

Front face of the pillar: ^{square} hole between

11 cm diam. } pendant leaves, smaller square hole
8 cm diam } below capital To take 2 horizontals

Lower: For wood standard for ensignia or for banners

Down face of column below lower hole are two protrubance like small breasts with a groove between them To take vertical pole of insignia

p. 163

END PILASTERS

M.S. - projects .40 cm

Flat faced corner framing enclosing 4 stems with half column

Half-round column .50 from pilaster face

↳ .70 cm diam.

M.N. Rectangular pilaster, flat inside corner w/ face and exterior corner molded of stems

Lover, degrees I

Mansion of North KheKher Frieze

p. 166 f

East Across total facade, between pilasters
and between columns

p. 167

Hieroglyph

MANSION OF SOUTH BUILDINGS

W: Court - West wall 2.10 thick

Open door simulated

N: Facade of M.S. $9^{\circ} / 81^{\circ}$

S: Massif of Heb Sed

Court wall is parallel

P-shaped monument at S end 3.80 across

~~T~~

Tremendous fissure traverse court E-W, filled w/
masonry, used for access to Pit I

Side ~~and~~ winding passage C to niched
sanctuary, D $\rightarrow$ Simulated open door

Offering niche for pit P₁ (?)

Facade with 1' single ~~plot~~ plant decor
only - base, probably emblematic plant
of S - lotus

Mansion of North Buildings

East facade of court - 3 papyrus columns
with triangular stem

Most ancient of ~~paper~~ papyriform columns

Nick Fairplay

Zoser panel $9' \times 3' = 81^2$
 9^2 ft a day @ 6 in depth

$9^2 / 81^2$ days per panel w/
one man

~~27~~ ft/day
2 x 3 ft/day
maybe 3 x 3/day

~~Crew of 100~~
~~1500 panels~~
~~9 / 1500 panels~~
1500 panels
x 9 days
365 / 13,500 days
man
9 days
36.98 years one man

Crew of 100 $\frac{135}{13,500}$ man days

135 days

Mansion of N.

Buried Tumuli

Filled platform 4.10m above ground
 Buried vaulted structures cased w fine limestone
 within fill D, E & F
 E Building abutts M.N. on its W. side
 Other vaulted structures S & W of D
 entirely destroyed - once buried w/in platform

WEST
 p. 175
 4 Rectangular structures J, K, L, M once
 cased in fine limestone, vaulted, buried
 within debris of platform

N. Court

Entered from serdab court @ N simulated open door
 Irregular court laid out E-W
 3 groups of chapels

1st Group - entered @ R

2nd Group - entered by simulated open door @ T
 possibly ^{wf-facing} facade above inner court like
 chapels of Heb Sed court

3rd Group - entered by simulated open door
 Square court with alabastr vase sunk in
 ground
 Small rectangular chambers on S N & E

Bounded by
 thick wall on N (N wall lit enclosure), original
 NE entrance

SERDAB COURT

Contrary to later more common serdab chambers,
placed projecting from pyramid face

M. A box

Inclined 17° to vertical, parallel to incline
of pyramid face

2 holes not necessarily contemporary

2 projecting side walls with representations
of open doors - double ~~leaf~~ leaf door
swung open wide

Blind corridor behind serdab penetrates
pyramid masonry to P1 with turn to E
into small chamber. = Earlier serdab of
P1?

N end of court walled off into smaller
court

W wall of smaller court had engaged fluted
columns

Chamber O off ^{Vestibule} corridor behind columned wall

M = Statue?

Chamber S off N end of vestibule

M Another Statue?

↓ Actually carved in relief on 3/4 projecting
from corner of backing block

Kind of partition

5 traverses - 2 closed, 3 open

N Temple

Lover, degrés, I, p. 75

E face only face free, W & N faces
bounded by massif forming terrace

Temple roof about 1.50 m above (p. 180)

Side entrance via winding passage

Maze-like narrow corridors

1.3 m wide measuring off plan Pl. XII

.99 between jambs, or .66 N entrances

Small chamber U - principal point in
temple - statue of King?

Similar chamber to W for false door or
stela?

Door - simulated open

Swing open against N wall

Through doorway, one ascends to ^{2m-high} platform on
which temple built

2 Chambers entered via corridor M
with basins, drains

Inner courts I and II

Each w/ 2 engaged columns on S.

p. 74

Fluted Column Facade

Each court - 2 pair fluted columns

↓ Actually carved in relief as $\frac{3}{4}$ projecting
from corners of backing block

Kind of portico

5 traverses - 2 closed, 3 open

Temple
badly
denuded

Like
T, Entrance

Colonnade

vs.
to be
building
dummy

N. Temple

Lower, degrees 2

20 flutes like Greek Doric columns

p. 75 - 3 Root terrace of temple formed of stone beams with rounded undersides imitate wood beams

- Tops of beams not browned by sun nor finished - covered by layer of clay

Top of temple forms molding - flaring cornice like Temple T around court interior.

These actual load-bearing columns, first attempt at a portico

Mc

Note:

2 Courts

2 Porticoes

2 inner sq. chambers

↳ Chamber U and mate to

North

for statue

2 Libation chambers

E side Corridors stairway

~~Red~~ Doubling of major elements

Mc

Accessed only by entry below, circumambulating

entire temple to NE Corner, proceed up

and ~~west~~ ^{south} above lower entrance to north

Descent to substructure begins N of temple in extended platform, becomes subterranean under court II

Western Tumuli

3 Tumuli E → W
I, II, III

Tumulus I

Panelled E wall shared w/ South Court
Top is terrace 5 m. above ground level in court

Tumulus II limiting on W is higher

Abutts pyramid at SW corner and leans against it for entire length

Casing of pyramid only begins above level of Tumulus I terrace @ 4.70 m

T₂ comes around NW corner ^{to join} terrace extending from temple, band ~~area~~ of T₂ terrace continues along E side of temple terrace

Tumulus Lower: Here again Pyramid (and temple) support tumulus and preexisted (note: contra Stadelmann)

Vast massif formed by partition walls between which filling of waste material

Tumulus II

Separated from T₁ by trench 2.80 m wide
Filled in Dyn 3 with stone material
1.25 W of edge of trench, is casing @ 6° incline 3 m thick against 2nd casing

Andy Obermann

First of casings hardly erected

Whether destroyed mostly, or having served
a finish never put in place

2nd casing, elevated 2.50 above level of terrace

Superstructure 25 m wide x 400 m long

3 m above level of terrace Tumulus I

Similar in form and construction to S. Tomb

but vaster

Cross section lightly vaulted top

Access to subterranean galleries

P₄, P₅, P₆, P₇

And descending galleries E at N end
of tumulus.

As Fitch thought, galleries were mines for
"great quantities of clay for core masonry
of massifs"

Tumulus III

Belonging to enclosure wall

2 parallel walls spaced 17.60

W. 6 m } thick

E 5 m }

Filled w/ debris

Small house found buried in debris fill, 120 m
from N end of massif

Summit level with cart walk behind parapet

N. Court

Lower, degrees V, 183f.

MAGAZINES

Massif of N. Enclosure wall.

Instead of 2 parallel walls, have 4

Behind fine paneled limestone exterior wall,
rubble wall 4 m wide

Then small walls, 1.10 m bond to first
by partition walls - 90 spaced 2m
forming regular partitions

2nd set of partitions between walls 1.10 m wide
N. Court, on S, 1.65 m wide

Aspect of magazines, a heap of grain (barley)
collected from one of enclosed spaces
"Windows" in ends of magazines facing central
corridor

Pit in central corridor 60 m west of platform
Gives access to subterranean magazines
where first food fruit, bread

Lower p. 184. These subterranean actual
galleries counterpart to dummy dummy
galleries in massif above

Central alley above must have been left
free for access to Pits to fill magazines after
harvest

Note
Compare platform
with gallery arrangement
at back of platform
at Amarna, Hall "in
Heraopolis Temple
= Receipt of
offerings over the
wall into temple
precinct

Lover, de grés I, 185

NE angle enclosure wall - No core wall, only
outer fine limestone bastioned wall 1.75 m thick

Area particularly overturned, disturbed

Large breaks in Enclosure wall 25-70 m

west of NE corner to take away stone
during quarrying

Or not completed except outer casing

Found here blocks of parapet and
w/ small relief rectangles indicating
outer fine wall was completed

N. Court p. 185

PLATFORM

2.80 m higher ground level than base of other
structures in enclosure

Platform 15 m on a side

cut out of rock

Stairway to South

Rock cut wall Fine limestone casing around core not

At South completely finished to corner

Lover: gigantic table of offerings

Rock on upper part of platform slightly cut down

8m sq. raised in center

Sq. hole to West of stairway, 2.5-3 m X 1.50 m deep
sim. to pit in front of S. ~~camp~~ platform stairs?

Enormous numbers of blocks around platform
and chips

Contents for partition walls? - Destroyed, especially
S. of platform

N. Court.

Lower, degrees, I p. 186

RAMP

p. 185

Debris near NE of platform is vast ramp

p. 1

to carry material over the enclosure wall.

For builders to bring material after Enclosure
Wall finished

p. 186

Passages along E & W sides of platform
lead to long corridor sanctuary
in N. Enclosure wall

Originally gave access to Pits 8 & 9 in
Magazine corridor

N Area not intended as a court but vast
dumping area from other constructions

Possibly intended small court S. of platform
access via descending stairways from terrace

Lower terrace than that around Temple
(by 2.80m possibly)

Rock Cut Tombs

At C 4 tombs descend to common
gallery w/ series of chambers

2 alabaster lion head tables from here

DRY MOAT

Swelin

Pyramid Studies

p. 13

Area 750 x 600 m

Width 40 m

Depth to 26 m

Complex at Netjer, Khaf more to S and W

Channels show on aerial photos as shallow depressions of cleaner or more undisturbed sand

N Side of S Channel ^{outer} not exposed

E Channel never excavated; shows in aerial photographs, so NE corner; runs $\approx 60-20$ m. E of Userkat Pyramid, ≈ 120 m from E. Enclosure Wall

p. 17

N Channel - 70 m from N. Enclosure Wall

W Channel SW Corner is 40 m north of Sekhemkhet Pyramid

p. 19

Ahmad Mousse poked up ^{west} edge of channel clearing tomb group east of Ptah holes ≈ 105 m from W. Enclosure Wall

Inner S. Channel

S edge to N of Unas complex

N side few meters from S. Enclosure Wall

Possibly 27.5 m deep

p. 20

How was Dry Moat crossed?

p. 21 Ascending ramp on inner ^{sides of} S. Channel

FIRST STAGE - NETJERYKHET

5-6th Dynasty tombs built on platform between moat and Enclosure wall

Rock cut tombs in walls.

Mc.

PARALLELS

Nearest parallel perhaps the Osireon at Abydos - so whole Netjerykhet complex on island

Stylized island of Nile?

Quarry - source of local stone?

Mantabas M-3

Mantabas at N & S

S. Altar

B-shaped Monuments

Hab Seal Charvats

O'Connor Expedition, Vol 23, No 3 (1991)
and Collection of Monuments

FIRST STAGE - NETJERYKHET

Swelin

p 63

Enclosure - enlargement by extending E wall
N-ward and S wall Westward
New walls on N & W sides

NE
entrance

{ N wall and NE entrance still seen behind
Mansion of the N
Comp. Khasekhemwy enclosure & Western Mastaba

Building Askew

{ Comp. Peribsen, Khasekhemwy
at Abydos, possibly Hierakonpolis Open
Court

S Tomb

Mastabas M1-3

Mansions of N & S

{ Off center to N-NW like
Mound in Hierakonpolis Temple
enclosure and Khasekhemwy
Funerary Palace

S Altar

B-shaped Monuments

Heb Sed Chapels

O'Connor / Expedition, Vol 33, No. 3 (1991)
and Followers of Horus

Stages - Netjaykhet

Lower, Pyramid Studies

p. 6 summarizes Kaiser - 'gradual change from mastaba - pyramid accompanied by gradual development of complex'

Lower: change not at all gradual

M2 is simple revetment to protect M2

M3 simple elongation to E

M1-3 changed all at once - new masonry style

p. 7 As Kaiser, thick wall of black masonry limiting Maeson Nord is probably first N wall of complex

But abutment of this wall to E Enclosure wall where false door bastion exists, is not acceptable

So: earlier wall not niched, or mudbrick

Or thick wall in question is not outer N wall of first stage but inner wall for massif

p. 9 "Out of question that heb sed court chapels originally constructed in three groups

No finished surfaces buried within 'later' massif masonry

Same goes for Mansions of N 95.

Simulation architecture vs Functional

} Symbolic for Ka of King in Afterlife
Functional to carry out funeral ceremonies

Lower, Pyramid Studies

p. 9 Simulation - Symbolic

Heb Sid chapels + Temple T
Maze of corridors in SE Massif
Mansions of S + N

Functional - functional

40 columns of Entrance Hall
Transverse Hall at end of Entrance Hall
Sanctuary of 'Building Askew'
Triple Niche sanctuary @ SE Corner of Pyramid
Offering place ~~at~~ in massif under cobra frieze
Temple N of Pyramid

Kaiser's criterion to date fictive architecture
to first stage, architecture actually entered
and functional to later stage, is not
applicable

Askew quality, by 1.5° of face of Sanctuary
and therefore Entrance Hall

Buildings Askew in Abydos Forts
considerably greater deviation

p. 11 Lower: deviation simply governed by fact that
W exit in S. Court gives line off-parallel to
S Enclosure wall

So first enclosure wall more simple - not bastioned
as in 2nd stage. Present Enclosure Wall built
after Entrance Colonnade, so E doorway in largest
bastion did not align with exit

Lauer, Pyramid Studies

p. 11

Lauer approves idea of Kaiser that relates doubling of tomb to 2 chamber tombs at Umm el-Gaab at end of predynastic

But doubling not, as Kaiser proposes, at Abydos itself since Djer - Umm el-Gaab and Valley Enclosure - because there is no trace at last place of royal sepulchre

Lauer sticks to hypothesis doubling took place at Saggara - Abydos, real tomb vs cenotaph, until Zoser complex.

Revised
 Books
 1911 p. 56
 Zoser

	Nathankhat	Sakankhat	Zawisat Area	Warden E	Warden F
Lowers	12	14	14	7	8
Angle of incline	74°	71-75°	62°	74°	74°
Steps	6	7			

Concise

Sekhemkhet p. 52

One step only remains

400 feet sq. - larger than Djoser

Unfinished state, height 23 feet

14 skins (accretion layers)

Angle of incline $71-75^\circ$

Each pair of accretions = 1 step as Djoser

So completed $\Delta = 7$ steps in place of 6

230 feet finished height - 30 ft. higher than

Djoser

Blocks roughly squared, set in tuffa mortar

taken from tunnelling, underground passages
with limestone chips mixed in.

laid in alternate headers and stretchers
like mudbrick

Boundary stela of Djoser found reused in
masonry - so later

Reisner

BmFA

1911 p. 56

Zawiyet

	Netjerykhet	Sekhemkhet	Zawiyet Aryen	Maidun E ₁	Maidun E ₂
Layers	12	14	14	7	8
Angle of incline	74°	$71-75^\circ$	68°	74°	74°
Accretions					
Steps	6	7			

Note: MR Part II Addenda

Collapse of corridor ceiling during construction. Was Sakhamkhot left incomplete because builders feared structural failure?

Revised
Part II
1911-1912
Subject

Number	Section	Notes	Remarks
1	1	1	1
2	2	2	2
3	3	3	3
4	4	4	4
5	5	5	5
6	6	6	6
7	7	7	7
8	8	8	8
9	9	9	9
10	10	10	10

Later Step Pyramids Gen

Huni - name on one of Elephantine Pyramid

So builder of 7 provincial pyramids?

Symbol of ^{presence of royal Majesty} centralized state now

germinated along Nile Valley

see Stadelmann: Given up when Sneferu began

first of lasting royal residences

prov. ~~pyr.~~ pyramids given up

Sekhemkhet - When an alabaster coffin dropped into
burial chamber as temporary tomb
during building to already make
functional the rising mound as a
"possessor of life?" Compare evidence
of smashed alabaster sarcophagus in
Netjerikhet, pieces packed around
granite vaults.

No ba
formed, no
real personality
as King

Was 2-year old child in S. Tomb
actually Sekhemkhet? Not having gone
through his Khaperu, he could not be
buried in pyramid - only informed ka
so placed in S. Tomb. Pyramid given up.

Note
Sekhemkhet
burial scene
in West Mastaba!!

When Netjerikhet died - only male heir
an infant (Note # of infant burials
under Step Pyramid) He died @ 2 years
worth of pyramid building

Note - Turin gives Netjerikhet (Pjoser)
successor 6 years months?

Note (Lauer Histoire, p. 191 - Jewelry for
"tiny person")